

Faculty Focus Group Questions

*Artificial Intelligence (AI) refers to technology that allows machines to perform tasks typically requiring human intelligence, such as learning, decision-making, and problem-solving. AI tools include **generative tools** (e.g. ChatGPT, Gemini, Midjourney), **voice assistants** (e.g., Siri, Alexa), **recommendation systems** (e.g., Netflix, YouTube), **navigation apps** (e.g., Google Maps), **editorial & similarity detection tools** (e.g., Grammarly, Turnitin) etc.*

Part 1: AI Use and Institutional Support

1. What has been your experience using AI in teaching and assessment, research and administrative activities (give examples, if any)

Follow-up:

- What benefits or challenges have you encountered, particularly in the African higher education setting?

2. What aspect of teaching and learning might change at your institution due to AI

Follow-up:

- How do you perceive the threats AI poses to the job security of faculty in the long run?

3. Has the recent rapid development of AI tools changed how you assess student learning? If so, how?

Follow-up:

- Have you changed the grading policies and approaches considering the helping hand AI offers to students?
- How do you distinguish between what students have actually learned versus what they can do with the assistance of AI?
- Are there specific domains or methods set up to assess the authenticity of student submissions considering AI tools?

4. What are your views on integrating AI into the curriculum (if applicable, give an example)?

Follow-up:

- Does the fact of being an African Higher institution influence that view?
- Are there ongoing discussions in your department or institution regarding changes to evaluation metrics for faculty and students due to AI adoption?

Part 2: AI, Ethics, and Impact on Institutional Culture

5. What are your biggest concerns when it comes to the use of AI in teaching and research?

Follow-up:

- Have you seen examples where AI tools demonstrated bias or raised ethical concerns in your work?
- In your opinion how likely do you think AI will affect (positively/negatively) your role as a lecturer/researcher?

6. How do you see AI influencing the culture, practices or values of African higher education institutions?

Follow-up:

- How do you think AI interacts with traditional teaching methods in the local context?

7. In what ways is your institution currently, or could it potentially be, a leader or innovator in the field of AI in education, rather than simply a consumer of existing technologies?

Follow-up:

- Are there any projects (like capstone projects or research collaborations) aimed at developing AI tools locally in your institution?

8. What has been your experience in relation to the support you have received from your institution for the adoption of AI technologies, if any.